

Supporting Information for

A time-resolved single-cell roadmap of the logic driving anterior neural crest diversification from neural border to migration stages

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Supporting Information Text

PART A: Detailed description of the premigratory and early migrating neural crest clusters.

Also see Table S3: list of the 16 NC clusters and their top-genes

1- At EMT and migratory NC stage

Out of ten migratory stage clusters (c7-c16), we identified **five cranial NC cell subpopulations** based on the lack of *hox* gene expression and expression of known anterior NC markers. Of these, three were previously found in Briggs et al., 2018 (1): *rpe65+* NC cluster 10; *vim+*, *itga4+* enriched NC cluster 11; and *dlx2+*, *efnb2+*, *cyp26c1+*, *epha2+* NC cluster 15.

We uncovered two previously undescribed clusters: cluster 14, a population of NC cells expressing the canonical early neural crest signature (*tfap2b+*, *c9+*) without additional specific signature, suggesting that these cells, although adopting mesenchymal characteristics (*vim* expression), remain “unbiased” and potentially multipotent (Fig. 3); and cluster 16, a NC subpopulation (*tfap2a+*, *sox10+*, *sox9+*, *twist1+*), enriched for actin and myosin-like genes (*actc1+*, *myl1+*, *des+*) (Fig. S11). Despite efforts to identify c16-like cells in the embryo, we have not been able so far to find them by *in situ* hybridization or by RT-qPCR in the iNC assay. At those later neurula stages, other cells of the embryo start expressing *tfap2a* such as somite and pronephros cells (Fig. S11). Using SPRING representation of single cell data from whole embryos (1), we found that, in addition to the NC cells, a subset of somite cells co-expressed *tfap2b* and muscle lineage markers. We are thus still unsure of the origin and location of c16 cells *in vivo*. In contrast, we have further studied c14 cells in Fig.3 and Fig. S2.

Additionally, we identified **three subpopulations of hox-positive rhombencephalic neural crest** previously grouped together. These cells form clusters 12, 13 and 9 and express *hoxa3*, *hoxb3*, *hoxd3* respectively, and are thus located at the vagal level. Cluster 12 includes cardiac NC (*egr2+*, *mafb+*) (2) while cluster 13 contains (*tnc+*, *ltbp1+*) ENS progenitors (3) (Fig. 2D and F).

2- At earlier neurula stages

Using specific gene signatures for clusters 1-6, we described the main characteristics of progenitors for each later stage NC subpopulation (clusters 7-16). **From the earliest stage of NC induction (gastrula stages 12-13), we detected three distinct trajectories emerging from the main canonical NC progenitor population (clusters 1, 2): an *hnf1b+olig4+* cluster 3, a *cyp26c1+* cluster 4 and a *rpe65+zfhx4+* cluster 10** (Figs. 2D, S12 and S13).

First, the previously undescribed *hnf1b+olig4+* cluster 3 is a pre-migratory cluster composed mainly of stage 12, 13 and 14 cells expressing pan-NB/NC markers such as *pax3*, *tfap2b* and *sox9*, as well as the dorsal neural gene *olig4*, *hnf1b*, the ngfr-related gene *nradd*, complement factor *cfb*, the posterior master regulator *cdx4* and a strong posterior hox gene signature (including posterior hox gene *hoxb8* and sacral hox genes *hoxc10/hoxd10*) (Fig. 2F and Fig. S12, S13B). Interestingly, this cluster seemed to respond to a combination of high WNT/low RA signals, in line with its posterior trunk signature (4). Indeed, early on, cluster 3 expressed canonical WNT signaling targets *axin2* and *cdx4* (5), as well as *dhrs3*, which attenuates RA signaling, is required for posterior axis formation and is usually mutually exclusive with *cyp26c1* expression (6, Fig. S13D). In cluster 3's older cells, expression of genes responsive to canonical WNT signals, *cdx4* and *sp5*, was

decreased, while expression of the non-canonical ligand *wnt11* was increased. Cluster 3's trajectory converged and merged with the enteric NC cells of cluster 13. While most of the enteric peripheral nervous system (ENS) arises from vagal NC, sacral NC cells contribute to cells in the hindgut. Cluster 3 posterior gene signature suggested that as early as mid-gastrulation stage 12, a minor NC progenitor population is already biased towards the future sacral NC fate, although those cells would emerge later on from the neural tube at tailbud-stage and give rise to the posterior ENS (7-9). Moreover, *wnt11* negatively regulates enteric NC differentiation (10), further suggesting that cluster 3 trajectory may consist of immature ENS progenitors. This cluster is the most posterior cell group found in this dataset (posterior trunk/sacral hox signature *hoxc10*). Identification of cluster 3 specific markers will enable future lineage tracing experiments to define the position and developmental contribution of these early progenitors of the enteric nervous system.

Secondly, appearing at stage 13, **the early-biased hox⁻ cluster 10** expresses *dmbx1*, *otx1*, *nrp2*, *lmx1b*, *rpe65* and *pax3*, thus contains early premigratory cranial NC cells (Fig. S13C). Bias towards cluster 10 was slightly noticeable at stage 12, as around 5% of the unbiased cluster 1 co-expressed *dmbx1* and *otx1*, which might indicate early fate predetermination. Moreover, 10% of the cluster 10 were cells of 13-14 stages (Fig. S3), the rest being later stages. This means that progenitors for cranial NC start being specified at neural plate stage, much earlier than anticipated.

Thirdly, the early-biased cluster, cluster 4, was composed of neural plate stage 13-14 progenitors of cranial NC populations with a **unique retinoic acid (RA) signaling-related signature**. It merged with cluster 6, (composed of stage 16-20 cells) and cluster 15 (composed of stage 22 cells). Cluster 4 specifically expressed genes encoding the RA-degrading enzyme *cyp26c1*, transcription factors *meis2* and *olig3*, neuropilin receptor *nrp1*, ephrin signaling receptor *epha2*, and ligand *efnb2* (Fig. S13D). Compared to the early unbiased cluster 1, cluster 4 exhibited increased expression of mature pan-NC markers *tfap2b*, *c9*, *snai2*, and decreased expression of multipotency marker *pou5f1* (Fig. 3). Cluster 4 expressed *hoxb1* and *hoxb2* indicating an anterior rhombencephalon position. More precisely *epha2* expression pinned those cells to rhombomere 4 (Fig. 2F) (11). High *cyp26c1* expression indicated low RA levels as essential to define rhombomere 4 identity (12). Last, *nrp1* specifically marks mouse NC from rhombomere 4 suggesting high conservation of the cluster signatures across vertebrates (13). Cluster 4's *cyp26c1/epha2* signature remained specifically expressed in the low-RA-dependent stream (c6, c15) from stage 12 to 22. Expression levels of genes encoding *epha2* and *efnb2* remained high while *cyp26c1* expression gradually decreased in later subpopulation of posterior CNC along with increased expression of genes encoding RA receptors (e.g. *rarg*) and cellular retinoic acid-binding protein 2 (*crabp2*) (Fig. S13D and S14). This revealed that the identity of rhombomere 4 NC was established as early as neural plate stages 13-14 under low RA signaling (cluster 4) while starting at neural fold stage 16 (cluster 6), later development of this lineage involved increased RA signaling. These observations highlighted the transcriptional outcomes of dynamic RA signaling in the progenitors of rhombencephalic neural crest forming the first (mandibular) and second (hyoid) arch stream respectively, anterior to the otic vesicle.

Fourthly and interestingly **at stage 16, two clusters were composed of progenitors for more than one trajectory ("bipotent clusters")**: a partially biased vagal cluster 9 (*mafb*⁺) resolving into both the cardiac NC cluster 12 and the ENSp NC cluster 13, and a cranial cluster 7 (*nrp2*⁺) which was equally linked to the *rpe65+zfhx4*⁺ cluster 10 and the *vim+itga4*⁺ enriched cluster 11 (Fig. 2D and S5). From late neural plate stage 14, the unbiased cluster 5, with higher expression of *c9*, *sox8*, *tfap2b* in comparison to the earliest unbiased cluster 1, started to split into the vagal-biased c9 (*mafb*⁺, *hoxd3*⁺) and the cranial-biased c7 (*rpe65*⁺, *dlx2*⁺, *hox*⁻) trajectories. Despite the global homogeneity within cluster 5, we detected a slight stratification for expression of neuropilins *nrp1* and *nrp2*, which would later mark NC cells emigrating from rhombomere 4 and from rhombomere 2 respectively (13). This suggested that within the unbiased cluster 5, a few cells

initiated a trajectory towards cluster 9 (vagal NC, *nrp1*, *mafb*, *cfi*, *meis2*, *mdk*) while others were shifted towards an anterior hindbrain trajectory (*nrp2*, *id3*, *ifitm3*, *alk*). This indicated that the SC transcriptomes identified an early bias in "bipotent" cell populations, opening hypotheses about gene regulations involved in each fate specification.

Finally, we detected three clusters (1, 5 and 14) expressing a canonical NC stem cell-like signature (*sox9*, *tfap2c*, *snai2*), together with high expression of pluripotency markers (e.g. *pou5f1*, *cmypc*, and *sox2*), throughout neurulation. The signature of these potentially multipotent cells, consisted of transcripts common to all NC cells, but was slightly variable across stages (Fig. 3C). At induction stages, this cell lineage expressed enriched levels of *zic1*, *zic3*, *tfap2c*, *cldn6* and *c3*, while at stages 18-22, it was enriched for *tfap2b*, *mycn*, *eef1b2*, *apoc1*, *vim*, *rack1*, *tfap2e* and *c9* expression. Quantitatively, about 72% of NC progenitors were found unbiased at induction stages (gastrula and neural plate stages 12-14), 15% at pre-migratory and EMT stages (stages 16-18) and 9% among tailbud stage 22 NC cells. Interestingly, according to PAGA, the latest unbiased population (c14) was transcriptionally equally close to the vagal (c9) and cranial (c7) transitional clusters, indicating that some stage 18-20-22 cells shared the unbiased pan-NC signature irrespective of their cranial or vagal levels of origin. Moreover, the later unbiased populations (clusters 5, 14) were mostly composed of premigratory cells with low *vim/fn1* expression and remained hox negative, generating NC cells which acquired a hox signature upon emigration state (e.g. hindbrain cluster 15 expressing *hoxa2*).

In sum, this detailed cluster analysis provided the temporal dynamics of gene expression underlying the main transcriptional states defining the various premigratory neural crest trajectories. It highlighted the early specification of several lineages, along with the maintenance of a NC stem-like population at all axial levels between cranial and vagal body axis regions. This analysis further provided a basis for the in-depth exploration of gene program variations which may drive branching at each bifurcation.

PART B - Supplementary Materials and Methods.

Experimental Design. Single cell transcriptomes from developing *X. tropicalis* embryos were scrutinized for NC development using machine-learning tools to infer the gene regulatory network (GRN) and the gene programs underlying branching of fates. These predictions were largely validated *in vivo* using micro-manipulations in *X. laevis* or *X. tropicalis* embryos followed by RNA-seq or ChIPseq.

Reference genome and gene symbol assignments. For bioinformatics analysis of SC dataset, we used the *X.tropicalis* v.10 genome assembly, gene models v. 10.7. Specifically, we used the file Xentr10-Gene-Sym-HUMAN-BLOSUM45.txt downloaded from Xenbase on Nov 5th, 2021. Thousands of genes in that transcriptome version lack interpretable gene symbols, though in many cases an unambiguous protein identity can be identified by sequence homology. To fill the holes in gene symbol assignments we assigned protein gene symbols to each transcript using a modified reciprocal best HMMER hit approach (14) based on a target reference set of curated human proteins.

scRNA-seq reads processing. Instead of collecting new materials we re-sequenced the whole-embryo SC-RNA libraries for developmental stages NF11 to NF22 (15) used in (1) using two flow cells (two lanes each) of NovaSeq S2 at 100 cycles setting generating a total of 12 billion reads. For SC analysis, we used the *X.tropicalis* v.10 genome assembly, gene models v. 10.7 (Xentr10-Gene-Sym-HUMAN-BLOSUM45.txt, Nov 5, 2021)

Compared to Briggs et al., 2018 (1), we selected a different aligner and scRNA pipeline since Bowtie (16), which was used in the InDrops pipeline (17), was not designed to align transcripts to the genome, and therefore is not splice-aware. A splice-aware algorithm does not align RNA-seq reads to introns, and identifies possible downstream exons trying to align to those instead. Moreover, using Bowtie for aligning reads to a transcriptome raises questions about choosing the correct transcript. Therefore, we chose STAR, since it is one of the best RNA-seq aligners and outperforms other aligners in terms of correctly and incorrectly aligned reads (18). Also, it is fast and there is no need to do preprocessing by removing bad quality bases or adapters as STAR does that internally (19). We used the DropEst pipeline (20). Recent benchmarking shows that DropEst exceeds other options in terms of sensitivity and efficiency (running time and memory use) (21). As a result, for v3 we used Indrops demultiplexing and soft filtering, then we generated tagged files similar to dropTag without considering reads base quality for barcodes, followed by alignment and quantification with STAR (outFilterMatchNminOverLread 0.44 --outFilterScoreMinOverLread 0.44) and dropEst using *X.trop* v10. After filtration by counts and genes numbers (>200 genes; >300 counts), we gathered a dataset of 177250 cells. In the cells of interest (Ectoderm and NC cells), mean counts number was 1778, and mean gene number was 1035.

scRNA-seq postprocessing. To process scRNA data we used Scanpy (22), a comprehensive scRNA pipeline that is functionally similar to Seurat (23). Firstly, we calculated the percentage of mitochondrial (MT) and ribosomal (RB) genes per cell by manually calculating the fraction of mitochondrial reads and ribosomal reads. As high MT proportions indicate poor quality cells (24), presumably due to loss of cytoplasmic RNA from perforated cells, we removed cells with a high percentage of MT/RB transcripts. Then, we removed gene sets which might affect the normalization step. These include foreign tissue contaminants, heatshock, ribosomal, clock and hemoglobin genes. For normalization, we excluded the expression of genes if their expression was more than 3 percent of the total expression of the cell, because it could greatly affect the resulting normalized values for all other genes (25). Next, we assessed the cell cycle dynamics. The algorithm calculates

the difference between the mean of the given list of cell cycle genes and the mean of the reference genes. To build such a reference, we randomly selected a set of genes that matched the distribution of the expression in the list. This way we got S phase, G₂/M phase scores for each cell. We did not regress out cell cycle effect because it had no significant influence. For normalization, we used scanpy function `scanpy.pp.normalize_total` without highly expressing genes and `target_sum=104`.

Embedding and Clustering Parameters: In our study, for different stages, we utilized a range of 3000-6000 highly variable genes in the initial data preprocessing step. The choice of the exact number of highly variable genes was made to balance the capture of informative features while avoiding potential noise. Similarly, the `n_neighbors` parameter for UMAP calculation was manually selected for each dataset. This allowed us to adapt to the local density structure of cells in different stages. **Batch Effect:** We decided not to apply batch correction methods in our analysis. This decision was based on the observation that the batch effect in our data was relatively low and primarily had a natural source - the distinct developmental stages being studied. Therefore, applying batch correction could have potentially obscured genuine biological variations associated with these stages. **Distinct Embeddings for Neural Crest Clusters:** we calculated separate PCA and UMAP embeddings for the subset of neural crest cells. This approach allowed us to specifically focus on the characteristics and relationships within the neural crest cell population without being confounded by the broader cell population in the dataset.

Doublet detection: We used Scrublet (26) algorithm to calculate doublet scores, a method specifically designed for detecting doublets in single-cell RNA sequencing data, thereby enabling the identification and exclusion of potential multiple artifacts from our analysis. Less than 1% (0.635) of cells were predicted to be doublets. We present an illustration of this analysis in Fig. S15.

Binary NC classifier. First, we generated a dataset by labeling cells as NC based on the previous differential expression analysis between clusters (1). For feature selection, we trained the LightGBM model (27) on the whole embryo dataset of 177250 cells, retrieved the top 2000 important features and used it for re-training the model (default setting with `n_estimators=500`). The resulting model detected NC cells in the test dataset from the *Xenopus tropicalis* dataset with accuracy 0.99 and F1 score 0.90. Only the trained dataset sample was used to get the top important features and retrain the model on the top 2000 features. To test the model robustness, we validated the NC classifier in the Zebrafish scRNA-seq dataset (28). We used a sigmoid function to smoothen the technical batch effect between the datasets. Genes that were not found in the Zebrafish dataset were replaced with NaN values (728 from top 2000 important genes were not found in the Zebrafish dataset). Finally, our model predicted NC cells in the Zebrafish dataset with AUC score 0.95 and F1 score 0.66 (in comparison, the random model with `strategy="stratified"` (<https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.dummy.DummyClassifier.html>) applied on the imbalanced Wagner dataset has F1 score=0.05). This result is striking because it was robust despite significant species-specific variations in the expression of classical NC gene markers between frog and fish, and despite a strong batch effect between the datasets (595 genes from the list of the most important genes for NC classification were missing from the zebrafish dataset). For example, the expression of `c9` and `snai2`, which are pan-NC genes in *Xenopus*, was drastically different in the zebrafish NC dataset. Yet, the classifier efficiently recognized NC cells in the fish neurula. This result confirmed the accuracy and robustness of our NC cells selection criteria.

GRN generation. One of the best tools designed to infer genetic co-regulation, GRNBoost2, is based on a gradient boosting machine and retrieves the gene regulatory network (GRN) from the expression data-matrix (29). Starting from a given list of TFs, this algorithm powerfully links genes with similar expression patterns in SC transcriptomes, providing "syn-expression groups" (30) at

the single cell level. Thus, GRNBoost2 provides a network of potential bidirectional gene relationships (including genes encoding TFs and other types of proteins). Through this algorithm, for each gene in the cell-gene matrix, a tree-based regression model is built to predict gene expression using the expression of TFs. Each gene-specific model produces a partial GRN with regulatory associations from the most predictive TFs for the gene. Then, all regulatory associations are pooled and ranked by importance to complete the GRN. The *Xenopus tropicalis* TF list (1417 TFs) was taken from *Xenopus tropicalis* TF catalog (31). We analyzed the resulting network of TFs and their targets using the networkx package and identified the most important nodes by calculating betweenness and degree centralities with `betweenness_centrality`, `degree_centrality` network functions.

Benchmarking SC-based machine-learning and in vivo experimental approaches to build the neural crest GRN. Our SC analyses provide a genome-wide connectome based on a total of 16978 interactions computed between 405 TFs (out of the initial list of 1417 TFs expressed in developing embryos) and 4532 other genes expressed in neural crest during gastrulation and neurulation. The biological significance of the network was validated using experimental analysis for three different NB/NC specifiers, Pax3 and TFAP2e, as transcriptomic interactions predicted using GRNBoost2 retrieved many interrelations supported either by direct TF binding (ChIP) or by TF depletion in vivo. However, when comparing the targets predicted with SC transcriptome modelling and experimental validation in vivo, we find that the fraction of gene correlations predicted with GRNboost2 also validated by ChIPseq was 7-9%, and also confirmed by TF depletion (which includes both direct and indirect targets) was 11-16%. Changing the network filtration criteria (weights, expression level) did not affect the proportion of validated genes. This means that despite the significant discovery power displayed by GRNBoost2 on a complex dataset, there is margin for increasing its specificity and accuracy. For example, GRNBoost2 did not link *tfap2e* to *hnf1b* (although confirmed by both ChIPseq and MO depletion), possibly because those genes have quite different expression patterns during the course of neurulation (Fig. S8D). Likewise, GRNBoost2 did not link *tfap2e* to *notch1* either (also confirmed with ChIPseq and MO) although they display closely related patterns. Another hypothesis for the incomplete coincidence of the predictions between MO/ChIP and GRNboost2 is that the dataset compiled for GRNboost2 includes cells of all available stages (due to the need for a large number of cells for modelling) while the MO/ChIP experiments were carried out at specific stages. Additionally, another limitation of GRNboost2 is its weak ability to predict the relationship between genes with different expression time-frames, i.e., when a gene A activates a gene B and stops being expressed in B-expressing cells.

RNAseq on dissected individual explants. The neural border and the neural crest were dissected as in (32, anterior neural border at stage 14) and (33) respectively. The explants were devoid of mesoderm contamination (for both NB and NC) or of ectoderm (overlying ectoderm for NC), as checked by RT-qPCR analysis of each explant. Total RNA from individual explants was sequenced by Illumina TruSeq. The 100 bp paired-end sequencing reads were aligned to the *X. laevis* genome version 9.2 using STAR and analyzed using String Tie. Differentially expressed genes were selected considering \log_2FC and expression difference in absolute values (abs. diff. ≥ 100 and ≤ 500 : $\log_2FC > 1.5$ or $\log_2FC < -1.5$; abs. diff. ≥ 500 and ≤ 1000 : $\log_2FC > 1$ or $\log_2FC < -1$; abs. diff. ≥ 1000 and ≤ 3000 : $\log_2FC > 0.5$ or $\log_2FC < -0.5$; abs.diff. > 3000 : $\log_2FC > 0.33$ or $\log_2FC < -0.33$).

ChIPseq parameters. Chromatin immunoprecipitation assay was performed as described in (34). Embryos were injected in both blastomeres at the two-cell stage with mRNA encoding Pax3-FLAG-HA (75 pg per embryo). Injected embryos were collected at mid-neurula stage 14 (100 embryos/sample) and processed according to the protocol. Sonication was performed using a 3.2

mm tapered microtip for 13 mm horn (Branson 450 sonicator). Anti-FLAG coupled to magnetic beads (Sigma M8823) were added separately to the chromatin. After sequencing, 100 bp single-end reads were aligned to *X. laevis* genome version 9.2 (Pax3) or *X. tropicalis* v10.0 (TFAP2e) using Bowtie2. Peaks were called using MACS2. For Pax3, we selected peaks common in three replicates, for TFAP2e we used stricter MACS2 score cutoff=500. Target genes were searched with bedtools (window size = 10kb). Peaks were visualized using JBrowse from Xenbase, https://www.xenbase.org/xenbase/displayJBrowse.do?data=data/xt10_0 for *X. tropicalis* and https://www.xenbase.org/xenbase/displayJBrowse.do?data=data/xl9_2 for *X. laevis*.

Note on Transcriptome and ChIP analyses (Fig. 4). There is a small inconsistency between pie plots and Venn diagrams; as *X. laevis* is pseudotetraploid, L/s copies of some genes are found one in the increased and the other in the decreased groups. For example, in the pie plot for Pax3 DE genes total is 1536 (357 + 1179). The Venn diagram shows 1528 (153 + 17 + 31 + 1327). This is because the L or s copies of genes AMFR, ATP1A1, DIRC2, EIF1, NR6A1, PPP1R8, WNT8A, and XETROV90007307M are in increased and decreased groups. So, if 357 and 1179 are summed up, they are counted twice, while each gene is counted once in the case of the Venn diagram. There is a similar small disparity for TFAP2e MO (for genes LOC101734821, SFRP2, XETROV90021076M).

iNC assay. The induced neural crest assay (iNC) uses co-activation of dexamethasone-inducible Pax3-GR and Zic1-GR in animal cap (blastocoel roof) ectoderm (35). In brief, 30 pg of Pax3-GR mRNA and 70 pg of Zic1-GR mRNA were co-injected into both blastomeres at the two-cell stage. A small animal cap ectoderm piece was dissected out at stage 9, and treated with 10 μ M of dexamethasone (or ethanol as solvent control) at stage 10.5. Sox9 was depleted using a previously validated morpholino (*sox9* MO, 10 ng) (36) and for gain-of-function, we used *sox9* mRNA (300 pg). At the desired stage, explants were harvested and processed by RT-qPCR (Table S10).

Total RNA isolation and RT-qPCR. Total RNA was isolated from explants using Trizol (Invitrogen) and isopropanol precipitation. For RNAseq on neural crest explants, each explant was processed individually. For animal caps in iNC assay, 8 to 10 caps were processed for each sample. cDNA was synthesized using MMLV Reverse transcriptase (Promega) and RT-qPCR was performed using Sso Advanced Universal SYBR Green Supermix (BioRad).

Fig. S1. A NC classifier based on *Xenopus* NC selection retrieves NC cells in other whole embryo datasets. **(A)** Expression of the top NC-specific genes in the NC compared to non-NC cells in a stage 14 embryo. Dot size: number of cells expressing the gene, color shade: average expression level. A binary classifier was trained on the frog NC/non-NC cells (see Methods). Using the whole embryo data matrix of gene expression, we selected the top 10% important features for NC detection. **(B-E)** In order to validate it in a whole embryo SC Zebrafish dataset (28), we removed genes present in frog data that were absent in the Zebrafish dataset: Using the subselected top genes, we re-built the model using frog data and obtained the following results: 0.99 accuracy and 0.90 f1 score on a test dataset. When applied to Zebrafish dataset, we obtained also very high scores: the accuracy 0.95 and f1 score 0.66 for 14 stage cells, indicating good initial NC cell selection. **(B)** Top features (gene) for NC classification using LightGBM model. X axis value is the relative importance of the certain gene for the NC classifier. **(C)** Confusion matrix indicates the true/false positive and the true/false negative scores for the results obtained on the Zebrafish dataset for stage 14. **(D)** ROC curve for the binary NC classifier indicates high AUC score of 0.95, meaning high recovery of true positives by the model. **(E)** UMAP for Zebrafish stage 14 hpf cells (left) with model-predicted NC cells. The model accurately identifies the cluster of interest (NC – green/black) despite the technical and biological batch effects between *Xenopus* and Zebrafish datasets.

Fig. S2. Genetic signature of different NC clusters. (A) UMAPs depicting expression of cluster marker genes across the NC dataset. (B) Each cluster presents various levels of expression of mesenchymal state/EMT markers and migration regulators. Bar plots with mean normalized expression for each cluster for *vim*, *twist1*, *mmp14* and *fn1*. (C) Hox gene signature of each cluster used to approximate their position along the antero-posterior body axis. The most anterior NC cells (cranial) do not express hox genes (hox-negative domain). The most anterior hox gene expression is seen in the rhombencephalon, where the hox code is well described: *hoxa2*, *b1*, *b2* at rhombomeres r2-4 levels, *hoxa3-b3-d3* at r5 and posterior levels, *hoxa4-b4-d4* posterior to r6. Posterior hox 7-11 genes show expression in spinal cord. In this study, only c3 and c13 express posterior hox genes. (D) UMAP plots depicting expression of pluripotency-related markers. (E) Proportions of the “unbiased” cells at each developmental stage of the NC dataset.

Fig. S3. Developmental stages per cluster. Pie-charts represent the proportion of cells at each stage in each cluster. Some clusters include cells of 6 successive developmental stages, e.g., cluster 10; while other are almost exclusively found at one single stage.

Fig. S4. ChIP-seq and RNAseq controls and validation. (A) Control for Pax3 ChIP: In the absence of a ChIP-grade antibody against *X. laevis* Pax3, we have expressed a FLAG-tagged Pax3 at low-levels *in vivo* (75 pg of mRNA encoding a C-terminally FLAG-tagged Pax3): this dose only slightly increases *snail2* expression, a known Pax3 immediate-early target (37). (B) For TFAP2e, a similar test of low perturbation was done after injecting low amounts of the FLAG-tagged construct. (C) A transient transgenesis approach allowed validating the specificity of the DNA fragments bound by TFAP2e: the TFAP2e-FLAG fragment bound upstream of *snail2* gene controls expression of a GFP reporter in the neural crest *in vivo*. Mutation of this element using Crispr-Cas9 mutagenesis eliminates *snail2* expression *in vivo*. This suggests that the putative target genes identified here display specificity, even if a similar formal validation of the peaks of interest for each gene remains necessary. (D) Detection of FLAG-Tfap2e from *X. tropicalis* embryonic extracts. The detection is target-specific since Tfap2e MO treatment leads to the loss of the band. (E) The expression levels of the genes top-scored with GRNboost2 for Pax3 or TFAP2e were tested after Pax3 or TFAP2e depletion in NB/NC *in vivo*. Several of them were strongly decreased after Pax3 or TFAP2e depletion (e.g. *bms1* or *sox10* respectively). Others were unchanged meaning that, despite similar transcriptome dynamics at the single cell level (evaluated by GRNBoost2), there was no major functional regulation by either Pax3 or TFAP2e *in vivo* at the considered stage (unless unknown compensatory mechanisms were to apply). (F-G) GRNBoost2 predicted targets of Pax3 (F) and TFAP2e (G) validated by ChIP-seq. (H) Random sampling (bootstrap) was used to test the average number of genes present in the intersection by the three methods if random chance was applied to these datasets. At random, an average of 3 genes would be found in the intersection compared to 17 genes identified for Pax3 or 20 for TFAP2e, which represents a significant enrichment in putative important targets.

Fig. S5. Early-stage biased NC clusters. (A-B) Comparison of early-stage bipotent NC clusters – cranial vs vagal states. UMAP plots for vagal (clusters 9, 12 and 13, **A**) and cranial (clusters 7, 10 and 11, **B**) specific markers. **(C)** In order to identify potential early bias in the globally homogeneous cluster 5, cells located around the bifurcation between clusters 1 (dark blue), 5 (purple), 7 (pink), and 9 (cyan) were sub-selected. Cells expressing *nrp2* or *mafb* above 80 percentile were highlighted. This revealed that cluster 5 presented a minor predisposition for either *mafb* or *nrp2* expression. Tables depicting cluster-cluster similarities calculated with PAGA. PAGA revealed that *nrp2*+ cells of cluster 5 were 7 times more similar to the cranial state (cluster 7) than to the vagal state (cluster 9). Conversely *mafb*+ cells of unbiased cluster 5 were 1.5 times closer to the vagal state than to the cranial.

Fig. S6. To test branching analysis predictions, we used *in vivo* depletion of either Pax3 or TFAP2e followed by RNA sequencing, and tested the changes in expression of the late genes in Pax3 or TFAP2e-related branches: Pax3 depletion leads to reduced expression of genes like *rpe65* (A, cranial c10) and *hoxb6* (B, vagal c13) while TFAP2e depletion leads to reduced expression of genes like *dlx2*, *tmem119* and *adam11* (C, cranial c11).

Fig. S7. Low-level depletion of TFAP2e affects NC cell specification partially. Depletion of TFAP2e was done using low-level (10 ng MO per cell, ¼ cell stage), in order to lower the effects on NC cell induction. *In situ* hybridization for *snail2* (**A**) or *twist1* (**B**) shows that this results in a moderate decrease in about 50% of the embryos. Cell migration assay depicted in Fig. 6B-D aimed at monitoring the distance of migration from those remaining cells, after backgrafting into a host embryo.

Fig. S8. Complements on neural border signature validation; validation of epistasis prediction between *Pax3*, *Sox9* and neural crest specifiers *snail2*, *cmyc* and *c3*, using inNC assay.

(A) UMAP plots for genes marking the 3 major ectoderm areas: *sox2* is enriched in the nascent neural ectoderm while *krt12* (epidermal keratin 12) is highest in the non-neural ectoderm. NB zone does not display a specific gene signature so far (usually depicted by *pax3* expression or overlapping expressions of ventral (*tfap2a*) and dorsal (*zic1*) genes, red cells in A, located across dorsal and ventral clusters). This analysis described a larger enriched signature (Fig. 7). (B) Pax3 depletion in NB changes in expression of the new NB signature genes. (C) *In vivo*, Pax3 depletion impacted expression of several NB->NC branch-specific genes, including *sox9*, *c3* and *foxd3*. (D) NNE1->PC gene program, (E) NNE1->later NNE (NNE2) gene program. (F) Connectome and scFates branching analysis revealed that Pax3 was an important node in the predicted GRN and an early gene for branch NB->NC. The Ectoderm connectome suggested a novel epistasis relationship between *pax3*, *sox9* and other downstream NC specifiers such as *snail2*, *c3*, *cmyc* and others. (G) To test for the epistatic hierarchy of Sox9, we used the well-defined inNC assay and checked the expression of NC specifiers at different stages by qRT-PCR. (H) At stages 12.5 and 14, Sox9 is essential for activating the downstream NC program: knockdown of Sox9 leads to significantly decreased expression of NC specifiers *snail2*, *cmyc* and *c3*. A – uninjected whole embryo, B – uninjected animal caps, C – *pax3*-GR + *zic1*-GR injected caps, D – *pax3*-GR + *zic1*-GR + *sox9* MO. All conditions were normalized to condition C of their respective stages. (I) Gain-of-function of Sox9 leads to significantly increased *snail2* expression levels, even at gastrula stages 11 and 11.5, time points at which *pax3* + *zic1* activation does not yet induce *snail2* expression in inNC. All conditions were normalized to condition C of stage 12.5. A, B, C – same as in (H), E – *pax3* + *zic1* + *sox9* mRNA. Error bars : SEM, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.01$, **** $p < 0.0001$.

Fig. S9. (follow-up of Fig. S8) validation of epistasis prediction in iNC assay: effect on *cmyc* and *c3*. Unlike *snail2*, gain-of-function of Sox9 is not sufficient for increasing expression of other NC specifiers such as *cmyc* (A) and *c3* (B), showing the possible requirement of other gene functions. All conditions were normalized to condition C of stage 12.5. A – uninjected whole embryo, B – uninjected animal caps, C – *pax3*-GR + *zic1*-GR injected caps, E – *pax3*-GR + *zic1*-GR + *sox9* mRNA. Error bars: SEM, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$.

Fig. S10. Markers for NB zone and early NC. (A) Ectoderm UMAP plots for stages 11, 12 and 13 representing gene expression of the main markers for ventral, dorsal and neural border, across the gastrula stage ectoderm. **(B)** In situ hybridization patterns for genes marking the 3 major ectoderm areas at stages 12.5 (late gastrula) and 14 (neurula). Whole-mount *in situ* hybridization followed a protocol optimized for NC (38). On dorsal and lateral views, *sox2* marks the neural (dorsal) ectoderm while *krt12* (epidermal keratin 12) marks the non-neural (ventral) ectoderm. Unlike the other derivatives, the NB zone does not yet have a large and specific gene marker list and is usually depicted by *pax3* expression or the overlapping expressions of dorsal and ventral genes like *zic1* and *tfap2a* respectively (dorsal views and transverse histological sections after whole mount *in situ* hybridization). Importantly, the neural border area (red dotted line) can also be defined as a zone devoid of both *sox2* and keratin expression as early as stage 12.5. **(C)** Ectoderm UMAP and corresponding ISH images depict the earliest stages of detection of 3 well-known early NC markers. Low-level *sox9* is initiated at the prospective NC zone at stage 12. *Sox8* and *snail2* are detected at the early NC at stage 13. Yellow arrows point to the NC region. Scale bar, 500 μm .

Fig. S11. Analysis of cluster c16. *sox10*, *tfap2b*, *actc1*, *myl1*, *des* – positive cells of c16 were looked for in the whole embryo and in iNC assay unsuccessfully. **(B)** In contrast, we found somite cells at stages 18-22 co-expressing *tfap2b* and *actc1* and other muscle lineage markers. **(C)** SPRING plots (1) showing all cells from stage 18-20 embryos. An early somite cell cluster expressing *tfap2b* appears at those stages and co-expresses muscle lineage markers such as *actc1*, *des*, and *mylpf*. Thus, the initial unsupervised selection of *tfap2b*⁺; *sox10*⁺ cells may have captured those immature somite cells and inappropriately associated them with NC cells. In contrast, no expression of the muscle lineage markers was detected in the bona fide NC clusters (*sox10*⁺, *tfap2b*⁺, in blue) either by SPRING bioinformatics analysis, nor by *in situ* hybridization or qRT-PCR on whole embryos or on NC explants.

Fig. S12. New TFAP2e putative targets. Benchmarking GRNBoost2. We identified some targets of TFAP2e, confirmed with ChIP-seq and MO, which were not predicted by GRNboost2 (e.g. *hnf1b* and *notch1*). This may result from functional regulations creating different expression patterns or different temporal dynamics, or else expression in adjacent cells (non cell-autonomous regulations), which are all parameters for which GRNBoost2 would not identify linkage. For example, neither *hnf1b* nor *notch1* were predicted as TFAP2e targets: *hnf1b* displays a very different expression pattern compared to TFAP2e, in the NC dataset, while *notch1*, despite a closely-related expression pattern at the cluster level, may in fact display distinct cell-to-cell expression at the single cell level.

Fig. S13. Early-stage biased NC clusters. (A) From the end of gastrulation, three previously undescribed early trends emerge. Clustering of stage 13 cells only, followed by PAGA analysis identified their similarities with the stage 20-22 clusters: an olig4-enriched subpopulation linked to ENSp cluster 13; a zfhx4-enriched cluster related to rpe65+ cluster 10 and a third stage 13 subpopulation expressing cyp26c1 linked to the cranial NC branch (clusters 4, 6, 15). (B) UMAP plots for the early-biased NC subpopulation expressing hnf1b, cdx4, nradd and posterior hox genes. In addition to cluster-specific hnf1b and olig4, dhrs3 is co-expressed with zic5, which specifically stays active during the whole “sacral” trajectory from stage 12 to late ENSp. (C) UMAP plots of genes specific for cranial rpe65+hox- NC subpopulation specific genes. (D) UMAP plots of genes specific for rhombomere 4, cranial NC subpopulations.

A

Fig. S14. Early posterior enteric cluster 4 and related late clusters 6, 15. (A) Line Plot for expression dynamics of rarg and cyp26c1 along trajectories of clusters 4, 6, 15. Cells within clusters are sorted according to pseudotime. **(B)** PAGA plots with rarg and cyp26c1 mean expression in each cluster. The complementary dynamics between levels of expression of the RA-degrading enzyme cyp26c1 and the RA nuclear receptor RARG suggests interesting temporal regulation of retinoic acid-related signaling during development of these NC populations.

Fig. S15. Doublet detection. Scrublet (26) algorithm was used to calculate doublet scores, a method specifically designed for detecting doublets in single-cell RNA sequencing data, thereby enabling the identification and exclusion of potential multiple artifacts from our analysis. Less than 1% (0.635) of cells were predicted to be doublets.

Table S1. Comparison of this Ectoderm/NC dataset with the relevant previously published scRNAseq datasets related to early NC development.

Compared to previously published SC transcriptome datasets of NC cells, our new dataset includes the largest number of premigratory and early-migrating NC cells. This allowed us to use complex ML approaches to reveal gene regulatory relationships.

Dataset	NC selection	Cell number	Depth	Timing	scRNA-seq technology	Reference
GSE108221	Chick, NC r4 stream, by manual dissection	469 NC	High	3 neurula stages (post-EMT)	SMARTseq v4	Morrison et al., 2017 (39)
GSE115331	C. intestinalis, tail region cells injected with Pax3/7>Foxc transgene	~5000 cells	High	1 late tailbud stage (~ post EMT)	10X Genomics Chromium	Horie et al., 2018 (40)
GSE112294	Zebrafish, WE/markers	63520 WE, 1770 NC	Low	7 gastrula & neurula batches	Indrops v1	Wagner et al., 2018 (28)
GSE106676	Zebrafish, foxd3+ cells	96 NC	High	1 gastrula & 3 neurula stages	SMARTseq2	Lukoseviciute et al., 2018 (41)
GSE113074	X.tropicalis, WE/markers	130000+ WE, 4700 NC	Low	9 gastrula & neurula stages	Indrops v2/v3	Briggs et al., 2018 (1)
GSE130500 GSE131688	Chick, cranial region (with foxd3 enhancer-Citrine) by manual dissection and FACS	124 NC (SmartSeq2), 3108 NC (10X)	High + Low	2 late neurula stages	SMARTseq2, 10X Genomics Chromium	Williams et al., 2019 (42)
GSE129114	Mouse, dissected trunk region, wnt1+/sox10+ cells, FACS	1107 NC	High	2 neurula stages	SMARTseq2	Soldatov et al., 2019 (43)
GSE162044	Mouse, r1 cranial region, wnt1+ NC, FACS	1741 NC	High	4 neurula stages	SMARTseq2	Zalc et al., 2021 (44)
GSE168133	Zebrafish, dissected PA1 migratory cranial NC, sox10+ cells, FACS	~400 NC (all stages), 420 NC (st 18hpf)	Low	6 neurula stages	10X Genomics Chromium	Tatarakis et al., 2021 (45)
GSE181577	Chick, WE/NB, markers	10358 HH4/6/7 WE, 6363 HH5 NB	High	4 gastrula stages	10X Genomics Chromium	Williams et al., 2022 (46)
GSE198494	X.tropicalis WE/markers	177250 WE, 6135 NC 17138 EC	Low	8 gastrula & neurula stages	Indrops v3	This study

Table S2. Top Ectoderm and NC specific genes for each developmental stage.

Using Leiden clustering and differential expression analysis we constructed two datasets: Ectoderm and NC. Table S2 represents the most specific genes expressed in the clusters in comparison to other cells of the whole embryo.

Cell type	NF stage	Cells number	Gene markers for cluster characterisation
EC	11	9190	SOX2, OLFM4, FOXI1, GATA2, SOX11
EC	12	3500	TFAP2C, C3, GATA2, OLFM4, ZEB2
EC	13	4448	TFAP2C, SOX9, OLFM4, LHX2
NC	12	623	C3, SOX9, ZIC1, SNAI2
NC	13	579	SOX9, SNAI2, C3, ZIC1
NC	14	416	SNAI2, TFAP2B, SOX9, SOX8
NC	16	882	TFAP2B, C9, C3, SOX10
NC	18	607	TFAP2B, C9, SOX8
NC	20	839	TFAP2B, SOX8, C9
NC	22	2253	TFAP2B, C3, C9, SOX10, DLX2

Table S3. Premigratory NC clusters characterization and key enriched genes.

Cluster number	Characteristics	Specific marker gene
1	Early unbiased	<i>tfap2c</i> ⁺
2	Early unbiased	<i>gjb1</i> ⁺
3	Premigratory sacral	<i>hnf1b</i> ⁺
4	Premigratory early R4	<i>cyp26c1</i> ⁺
5	Premigratory unbiased	-
6	Premigratory late R4	<i>cyp26c1</i> ⁺
7	Migratory bipotent cranial	<i>nrp2</i> ⁺
8	Migratory rhombencephalic	<i>hoxb2</i> ⁺
9	Migratory bipotent vagal	<i>hoxd3</i> ⁺
10	Premigratory early cranial	<i>alx1</i> ⁺
11	Migratory cranial	<i>itga4</i> ⁺
12	EMT cardiac	<i>egr2</i> ⁺
13	Migratory ENSp	<i>tnc</i> ⁺
14	EMT unbiased	-
15	Migratory late R4	<i>efnb2</i> ⁺
16	Migratory muscle-like	<i>myl1</i> ⁺

Table S4. Highly connected genes in the neural crest network predicted by GRNboost2.

Gene	Degree centrality	Betweenness centrality	Max. expression stage	NC specificity
TFAP2C	28.028933	21.510673	12	6.59
ZIC3	16.455696	7.885226	12	3.73
ZIC1	8.137432	2.351524	12	9.34
ZIC2	7.233273	2.026896	12	3.62
DMBX1	3.616637	11.876445	12	1.57
PAX3	3.435805	2.211830	12	5.93
SOX9	11.573237	8.575830	13	14.07
OLIG4	4.882459	2.642370	13	4.54
MAFB	7.956600	4.174946	14	09.08
SNAI2	5.244123	0.927599	14	20.03
SOX8	4.520796	2.071516	14	20.60
RPE65	1.446655	0.534404	14	6.49
TFAP2B	8.499096	4.135991	16	25.47
HOXB3	3.978300	0.959282	16	2.35
SOX10	3.797468	0.705758	16	15.40
NR6A1	3.797468	0.706433	16	9.18
ZFHX4	2.169982	0.791908	16	4.83
ALX1	2.169982	1.627017	16	3.69
EPHA2	1.989150	1.403078	18	3.77
E2F3	1.446655	2.256467	18	0.68
TFAP2E	5.786618	1.850976	20	15.21
EGR2	5.424955	2.505897	20	5.96
MYCN	17.359855	12.737248	22	8.81
DLX2	12.839060	8.413243	22	6.88
HOXD3	8.137432	3.417475	22	4.96
EEF1D	4.701627	0.795235	22	9.55
ZBTB16	3.074141	1.013930	22	2.80
TFEC	2.169982	0.562422	22	0.10
VIM	2.169982	0.879581	22	2.43

Table S5. Highly connected genes in the ectoderm network predicted by GRNboost2.

Gene	Degree centrality	Betweenness centrality	Mean nc/pc/nb specificity	NC specificity	PC specificity	NB specificity
TFAP2C	70.319635	6.203872	8.778883	17.587187	3.636364	5.113099
TFAP2A	67.123288	5.770185	11.238043	4.836522	-0.884711	29.762320
ZIC1	47.488584	1.674848	15.645578	18.120411	-8.226690	37.043015
HES1	30.136986	0.815641	13.273738	27.994427	11.076355	0.750431
SOX9	24.657534	0.463349	11.848502	38.367329	-4.275626	1.453803
MYC	17.808219	0.340629	9.269785	22.733620	4.699314	0.376421
SNAI2	17.579909	0.192783	7.027262	27.004408	-3.017278	-2.905344
PITX1	16.438356	0.115279	5.463268	-3.656815	21.928877	-1.882259
PAX3	14.611872	0.172905	5.509155	15.614752	-3.379381	4.292094
SOX8	12.100457	0.094409	5.176289	19.021635	-2.535636	-0.957131
C3	9.817352	0.019518	12.694010	36.559040	6.013386	-4.490397

Tables S6 and S7: Top-decreased genes after Pax3 or TFAP2e depletion.

Top decreased genes in Pax3 (left) and TFAP2e MO (right) samples with the absolute expression change > 1000.

Gene_name	log2FC	abs_diff
oxnad1.l	-4.471306	2796.0
pou4f1.2.l	-3.792479	1208.5
stxbp5-like.1.l	-3.573356	1134.0
loc100498469-like.l	-3.269686	1227.5
slc12a2.l	-3.269554	1988.0
gatm.l	-3.219859	11768.5
pnhd.s	-3.189243	1104.5
sox9.s	-3.160360	3605.0
hnf1b.l	-3.122515	3153.0
pygm.s	-2.895865	2087.5
olig4.l	-2.869639	1287.0
loc733561.l	-2.836421	1099.5
msx1.l	-2.815328	5604.0
hoxb1.s	-2.729814	1538.0
hnf1b.s	-2.690841	2215.5
h1foo.s	-2.681030	1277.5
hyou1.l	-2.640135	1544.0
hoxd1.l	-2.637859	1410.5
hoxd1.s	-2.594724	2475.0
msx2.l	-2.587375	3742.5
olfm4.l	-2.565518	5451.0
pnp.l	-2.480788	2625.5
dhrs3.l	-2.469848	2506.0
ppat.l	-2.468018	2416.0
vim.l	-2.450922	4834.0
prkaa1.l	-2.350497	1045.5
snrnp70.l	-2.320323	11492.0
cdx2.l	-2.289480	2395.5
sp5l.l	-2.267839	3598.5
msx1.s	-2.267784	2652.0

Gene_name	log2FC	abs_diff
sox10.s	-4.446147	6291.5
sox10.l	-3.973992	7541.0
sox8.s	-3.623336	2485.5
loc101735110.l	-3.294872	3226.0
loc100498368-like.s	-3.288774	6777.0
tp63.l	-3.282590	1379.5
fam212a.s	-3.190155	1215.0
fam212a.l	-3.189506	2014.5
tfap2b.s	-3.111449	2319.5
loc100498368-like.l	-3.058974	2636.5
foxd3.l	-2.979076	2062.0
adam11.l	-2.943961	1329.0
sox8.l	-2.803670	9715.0
endod1.l	-2.742037	1212.0
mafb.s	-2.642183	1447.0
kal1.l	-2.578369	1817.5
tfap2b.l	-2.529612	2642.5
mycn.s	-2.511291	1086.0
twist1.l	-2.453900	2819.5
twist1.s	-2.421903	2770.0
loc100124848-like.l	-2.401117	8166.0
fn1.s	-2.305269	4979.5
kiaa1217-like.l	-2.296111	1036.5
ahnak-like.s	-2.267407	3456.0
itln1.l	-2.252100	6428.5
lima1.l	-2.242827	2533.0
loc100497845-like.l	-2.208089	1035.5
itpr3.s	-2.194760	2438.5
aim1-like.1.s	-2.168639	1307.5
cmahp.l	-2.151611	1425.5

Table S8. Pax3 targets genes identified by ChIP-seq.

Top MACS2-scored direct gene targets bound by Pax3.

chr	start	end	score	gene
chr8L	99475396	99475464	580	ASTL3A.1
chr9_10L	349156	349253	518	ATP6V0A1
chr7L	92931087	92931289	487	HES3
Scaffold46	813190	813276	484	ASS1
chr2L	176448007	176448188	448	PRCP
chr8L	118795321	118795461	440	FLAD1
chr8L	118785517	118785631	440	PSMD4
chr7L	89910794	89910942	435	VPS13D
chr3L	130428472	130431136	417	S1PR2
chr7L	15405111	15405195	390	INPP5A.1
chr6L	86407631	86407987	374	LYRM4
chr8L	119048876	119048973	368	EFNA3
chr1L	144729397	144731409	358	TBX3
chr5S	17252239	17252405	341	ATF3
chr4L	141138945	141139207	341	ATXN7
chr6L	37364463	37364585	314	HDAC9
chr6L	124571856	124571969	312	ZFAND1
chr6L	124583418	124583619	312	CHMP4C
chr4S	38950018	38950121	307	NAE1
chr9_10L	65487732	65488499	291	SLC25A12
chr5L	51178347	51178965	288	PSEN2
chr1S	115523395	115523481	286	NRL
chr6L	39747334	39747730	286	EVX1
chr9_10L	30759439	30759550	279	TGM3L.4
chr2L	88024978	88025202	267	HPCA
chr6L	82762756	82762905	266	CDH20
chr1S	12094861	12094998	263	FGFR3
chr8S	33705393	33705520	248	FUBP3
chr8L	57452010	57452126	245	SELENOW1
chr9_10S	23803020	23803090	244	USP36

Table S9. TFAP2e ChIP-seq targets.

Top MACS2-scored genes targets bound by TFAP2e.

chr	start	end	score	gene
Chr7	2771023	2771259	1502	RBM20
Chr4	136928957	136929250	1360	PIM1
Chr10	10458652	10458795	1353	ARL5B
Chr10	10464454	10464497	1353	PLXDC1
Chr5	13534757	13535087	1326	PTPN14
Chr10	50539112	50539288	1235	ARPC1A
Chr10	50529349	50529522	1235	PRKAR1A
Chr10	15734843	15734962	1218	SMARCD2
Chr2	2687034	2687603	1212	BOC
Chr9	85342807	85342887	1199	TNS1
Chr6	90349120	90349399	1198	TFAP2A
Chr6	47572683	47572824	1180	RARB
Chr4	58757061	58757134	1176	ANKRD11
Chr4	48790141	48791762	1170	BCAR1
Chr7	18235059	18235409	1164	JMJD1C
Chr2	138639744	138639788	1159	RBMS2
Chr8	6618399	6618453	1159	NOTCH1
Chr8	142072529	142072579	1153	CCT3
Chr8	142086526	142086803	1153	GLMP
Chr2	40958194	40958575	1153	PKD3
Chr1	65662851	65663810	1145	SPRY1
Chr4	67913743	67913832	1139	KCTD15
Chr9	83910392	83910819	1130	TUBA4A
Chr1	206833365	206833506	1100	RNF165
Chr1	16309482	16311265	1095	DCTN1
Chr1	16305342	16305426	1095	ADAM33
Chr10	11004405	11005055	1091	ARHGAP23
Chr6	12882851	12882961	1084	DHX30
Chr6	12892165	12892295	1084	LIMA1
Chr4	35478920	35479123	1071	PPP1R14B

Table S10. PCR Primers used in this study.

primer name	purpose	sequence	reference
Snail2 Fwd pair1	ChIP-seq IP quality check	CCATCCCAACACCTGTCGTA	This study
Snail2 Rev pair1	ChIP-seq IP quality check	GCCCACCAGTTCACGTTCAT	This study
Snail2 Fwd pair2	ChIP-seq IP quality check	GCAATGCCTCAGCCTGTGAA	This study
Snail2 Rev pair2	ChIP-seq IP quality check	CAGCGCGTACTGCAATTCATTC	This study
Odc Fwd	qRT-PCR	GCCCTTTCTCCCTTTAACGC	(35)
Odc Rev	qRT-PCR	TGGTCCCAAGGCTAAAGTTG	(35)
Snail2 Fwd	qRT-PCR	CACACGTTACCCTGCGTATG	(47)
Snail2 Rev	qRT-PCR	TCTGTCTGCGAATGCTCTGT	(47)
Cmyc Fwd	qRT-PCR	AACGACAGCATTTCCAACGC	This study
Cmyc Rev	qRT-PCR	CGTCGCAGTCTTCATCCTCA	This study
C3 Fwd	qRT-PCR	CCTGTTGGGCAGGATTTG	(37)
C3 Rev	qRT-PCR	CGCAAGCCATGTTGACTCT	(37)
Dmbx1 Fwd	qRT-PCR	CCTCCAGCCATGCAGCATTAA	This study
Dmbx1 Rev	qRT-PCR	ATGTCAGCCAGTCTCTCTGC	This study
Rpe65 Fwd	qRT-PCR	GGCACCAGATGCCATTGAA	This study
Rpe65 Rev	qRT-PCR	CTTTCACATGTCTACCGCTGT	This study
Zfhx4 Fwd	qRT-PCR	ACACCACCAATCACAGGCAT	This study
Zfhx4 Rev	qRT-PCR	TCAGTGGGCAGTCTTTCACA	This study
Mmp14 Fwd	qRT-PCR	AAGGAGCATTTCATGGGCAGTGATG	This study
Mmp14 Rev	qRT-PCR	CCATCCAGTCGACCAAAAACGGA	This study
Fn1 Fwd	qRT-PCR	ACCTCAACTACACAGACTCGA	This study
Fn1 Rev	qRT-PCR	AGCTGCCATGGGACAGAATC	This study
Dlx2 Fwd	qRT-PCR	AGGATGGTCAATGGGAAGCC	This study
Dlx2 Rev	qRT-PCR	GCTCAGAAAAGGGCTGGGAC	This study
Twist1 Fwd	qRT-PCR	AATGCCACTACAGCTCAGGC	(35)
Twist1 Rev	qRT-PCR	GCCCTTTCTCCCTTTAACGC	(35)
MyoD Fwd	qRT-PCR	TACTGACAGCCCCAATGA	This study
MyoD rev	qRT-PCR	TGCAGAGGAGAACAGGGACT	This study

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